

**ISSUES IN DETERMINING PERFORMANCE FACTOR
DISAPPROVAL IN SMALL BUSINESS ENTERPRISES****Kaypnazarova Gulshad Khojamuratovna**

Associate Professor of Karakalpak State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18859141>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 26th February 2026Accepted: 27th February 2026Online: 28th February 2026**KEYWORDS**

From this point of view, it was proposed to introduce a special mechanism aimed at coordinating production factors

ABSTRACT

At the current stage of socio-economic development in Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to measures to solve problems related to creating a favorable environment for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, ensuring the sustainability of enterprises and increasing their economic efficiency.

At the current stage of socio-economic development in Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to measures to solve problems related to creating a favorable environment for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, ensuring the sustainability of enterprises and increasing their economic efficiency.

Ensuring the sustainability of enterprises and determining the main criteria for assessing the correspondence of economic resources or processes in small business enterprises to the status of a production factor requires scientific research aimed at preventing imbalances between production factors and reducing the risk of negative impacts on activities by forming groups to coordinate the mutual movement of resources between small business enterprises by agencies supporting entrepreneurial activity in the region, the level of proportionality of production factors in enterprises, systematic monitoring and diagnostics of the effectiveness of their use, the establishment of consulting services to ensure the current and future economic stability of the enterprise, and the development of forecast indicators of the impact of production factors in small business enterprises in the country on the volume of gross industry output.

In order to study the state of the balance between production factors and the problems of ensuring it in small business enterprises operating in Karakalpakstan, a social survey and monographic research were conducted with the participation of a number of enterprises. The results of the study showed that the issue of effective distribution of production resources is relevant for many enterprises in the region. In particular, a large part of the employees who participated in the survey noted the existence of a balance between production factors in their enterprises. This problem was especially pronounced in enterprises specializing in production. This situation is explained by the variability of the need for equipment, raw materials, materials and infrastructure and interruptions in the supply of resources. At the same time, it was found that the level of balance is relatively low in enterprises operating in

the service sector. The reason for this was the low need for material resources and the predominance of labor and organizational factors. In diversified enterprises, the problem remains at a moderate level due to the possibility of redistributing resources between production, trade and service areas. Thus, diversification of activities provides a certain stability in the management of production factors.

The survey results also showed that the majority of entrepreneurs consider it necessary to support local state and public authorities in ensuring the proportionality of production factors. This confirms that the institutional environment and organizational support are an important factor in the development of small businesses. In particular, local authorities, agencies responsible for the development of entrepreneurship, and trade and industrial structures are the main institutions that promote the effective use of resources.

From this point of view, it was proposed to introduce a special mechanism aimed at coordinating production factors. The main content of the mechanism is to strengthen cooperation between enterprises and coordinate the movement of resources. At the first stage, enterprises in the region will be grouped according to certain production factors. At the second stage, enterprises using similar raw materials and materials will have the opportunity to exchange information with each other via an electronic platform. This will allow them to quickly find partners in case of resource shortages or surpluses.

At the third stage, a monitoring center will be established to coordinate this process and help eliminate problems by collecting and analyzing data. If enterprises cannot resolve the problem through mutual agreement, the center will offer recommendations and practical measures based on economic calculations. Also, a resource reserve will be formed and, if necessary, market balance will be ensured by supplying raw materials or purchasing excess resources. In conclusion, effective management of production factors in small business enterprises should not be limited only to the production process, but also include its preparatory and planning stages. Thorough development of a business idea and business plan, preliminary assessment of resource needs and regular monitoring of their adequacy will increase the efficiency of enterprises. The proposed mechanism, in turn, will ensure the full use of resources, reduce the risk of imbalances, and ultimately serve the sustainable development of small business entities.

References:

1. Imaeva G. R. Theoretical and methodological aspects of studying the social role of small and medium-sized businesses // Monitoring public opinion: economic and social changes. 2015. No. 4. Pp. 141-153;
2. Kozma E. S. Sustainable development of small entrepreneurship as an indicator of the development of the PMR // Innovations in science: scientific journal. - No. 1 (77). - Novosibirsk., Publishing house ANS "SibAK", 2018;
3. Krotov I. I. Development of small entrepreneurship based on state and municipal orders (on the example of regions of the Russian Federation). Diss... Cand. Sciences. - Perm. 2015;
4. Abulkosimov H.P., Kulmatov A.A. The role of family entrepreneurship in the small business sector in Uzbekistan and ways of its development. Monograph. – T.: University, 2015. – 126 p.;
5. Aripov O.A. State regulation of small business and development of the business environment. Author..doc. in economic sciences. – T.: 2020. 72 p.;

6. Ibragimova M.M. Increasing the efficiency of small business and private entrepreneurship based on structural changes (on the example of the Namangan region). Author's thesis ... Doctor of Philosophy in Economic Sciences (PhD). – T., 2018.;
7. Murodova N.K. Improving the theoretical foundations of state support for small business and private entrepreneurship. Author....doc. in economic sciences. – T.: 2016. 107 b;
8. Muftaydinov Q. Problems of entrepreneurship development in the conditions of economic liberalization. Dis. ... iqt. science. dr. - T., 2004.

